

Comparative Analysis of Operative versus Conservative Treatment for Spinal Cord Injury: A Prospective, Case-Control Study in A Tertiary Care Hospital in Himachal Pradesh

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Received: 20-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 30-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This retrospective case-control study at Pt. JLN Govt Medical College, Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, evaluated the outcomes of operative versus conservative treatments for spinal cord injuries over 14 months with 91 participants. The study found that operative treatment significantly improved neurological function and quality of life compared to conservative methods, albeit with a higher rate of complications. These results suggest that while operative interventions offer more substantial recovery benefits, they also pose greater risks, emphasizing the need for careful patient selection and management strategies. This study contributes to the growing body of evidence that supports tailored treatment approaches for spinal cord injuries based on comprehensive risk-benefit analyses.

Keywords: Spinal Cord Injuries, Operative Treatment, Conservative Treatment, Neurological Recovery

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Introduction

Spinal cord injuries (SCIs) are among the most devastating traumas, leading to significant physical, emotional, and financial burdens for patients, families, and healthcare systems [1]. The management of SCI involves a complex decision-making process that includes choosing between operative and conservative treatment modalities. This choice is influenced by various factors including the nature and severity of the injury, timing of intervention, and the patient's overall health status [2,3].

In Himachal Pradesh, a region characterized by challenging geographies and a dispersed population, healthcare delivery is particularly complicated, especially for conditions requiring sophisticated interventions like SCIs [4]. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the outcomes associated with operative versus conservative treatments for spinal cord injuries in a tertiary care setting within this unique context [5,6].

This comparative, case-control, and prospective study will evaluate the efficacy, safety, and long-term outcomes of surgical interventions compared to non-surgical management. By systematically analyzing data collected from a tertiary care hospital in Himachal Pradesh, this study seeks to

identify which treatment modalities provide the best outcomes in terms of patient recovery, quality of life, and cost-effectiveness [7,8].

This study aims to evaluate and compare the outcomes of operative versus conservative treatment approaches for patients with spinal cord injuries at a tertiary care hospital in Himachal Pradesh. Specifically, this study seeks to determine the effectiveness, safety, and cost-efficiency of these treatment modalities in promoting recovery, minimizing complications, and improving the quality of life for patients. Through a prospective, case-control analysis, the research will provide critical data that can inform clinical decisions and potentially lead to optimized treatment protocols for spinal cord injuries in similar healthcare settings.

Methodology

This retrospective case-control study was conducted at Pt. JLN Govt Medical College, Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, spanning 14 months. The research aimed to compare the operative and conservative treatment modalities for spinal cord injuries within a tertiary healthcare environment.

Participants

The study involved a cohort of 91 patients who had experienced spinal cord injuries. Patients were divided into two groups based on the treatment they received at the onset of care: the operative group and the conservative group. Selection criteria were based on the medical records indicating the initial treatment approach prescribed by the healthcare professionals.

Data Collection

Comprehensive data were gathered from patient medical records, which included demographic details, specific characteristics of the injury, type of treatment administered, and subsequent health outcomes. Key outcome measures focused on neurological recovery, the occurrence of any treatment-related complications, and quality of life assessments conducted during follow-up appointments.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcomes assessed were:

- Neurological improvement, quantified according to standard recovery scales.
- The occurrence and severity of complications associated with each treatment modality.
- Quality of life post-treatment, evaluated using validated questionnaires specific to spinal injury.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using statistical software. Quantitative variables were analyzed using t-tests to compare means, while categorical data were examined through Chi-square tests for independence. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all tests.

Results

The study encompassed a total of 91 patients diagnosed with spinal cord injuries, distributed evenly into two groups: 46 patients received operative treatment, and 45 patients underwent conservative management.

Neurological Outcomes

- The operative group exhibited significant improvement in neurological function compared to the conservative group. Specifically, 39 out of 46 patients in the operative group showed marked neurological recovery, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

- In contrast, only 28 out of 45 patients in the conservative group demonstrated similar improvements.

Complications

- The rate of complications was higher in the operative group, with 15 patients experiencing various post-surgical complications such as infections and delayed wound healing.

- The conservative group reported fewer complications, with only 9 patients encountering issues, primarily related to immobilization and non-surgical management.

Quality of Life

- Quality of life assessments indicated that patients in the operative group generally reported better outcomes concerning mobility and self-care capabilities. The mean score on the quality-of-life scale was significantly higher for the operative group ($p < 0.05$).

- The conservative treatment group, while showing improvements, had a lower mean score compared to the operative group, reflecting more challenges in daily activities and overall satisfaction with treatment outcomes.

The results of the study suggest that operative treatment may lead to better neurological recovery and quality of life for patients with spinal cord injuries, despite a higher incidence of treatment-related complications. Conservative management showed fewer complications but did not achieve the same level of effectiveness in improving neurological function and quality of life as observed in the operative group. These findings underscore the need for a careful selection of treatment modalities based on individual patient conditions and the potential risks associated with each approach.

Treatment Group	Patients	Improved Neurological Function	Complications	Quality of Life Score (Mean)
Operative	46	39	15	8.2
Conservative	45	28	9	6.5

This table summarizes the key outcomes, including the number of patients who showed improved neurological function, the complications

encountered, and the average quality of life score for each treatment group.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that operative treatment for spinal cord injuries at a tertiary care hospital in Himachal Pradesh leads to more favorable neurological outcomes and an improved quality of life compared to conservative management [9]. While the operative group showed a higher incidence of complications, such as infections and wound healing issues, the significant improvement in neurological function and quality of life scores suggests that the benefits of surgical intervention may outweigh the risks in many cases [10,11].

However, the conservative group, despite fewer complications, showed lesser improvements in neurological function and lower quality of life scores. This could imply that while conservative treatment poses fewer risks, its effectiveness in terms of recovery and overall patient satisfaction is limited [12,13]. Healthcare providers must consider these findings and weigh the potential for greater recovery against the increased risk of complications when deciding on treatment modalities for spinal cord injuries [14]. This study also underscores the importance of individualized patient care plans and the need for rigorous follow-up to manage complications effectively when opting for operative treatments. The disparity in outcomes between the two groups also highlights the potential need for advancements in conservative treatment strategies to enhance their effectiveness [15,16].

Further research should explore the long-term outcomes of these treatments and examine the specific factors that may influence recovery and complication rates, such as the severity and location of the injury, patient age, and pre-existing health conditions. This will help in refining treatment protocols and improving the overall management of spinal cord injuries in similar settings [17-20].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Pt. JLN Govt Medical College in Chamba, Himachal Pradesh, provides compelling evidence that operative treatment for spinal cord injuries generally results in better neurological recovery and improved quality of life compared to conservative treatment, despite a higher complication rate. This highlights the necessity for a nuanced approach to treatment selection, where the potential benefits of operative intervention are carefully balanced against the risks. The findings advocate for enhanced protocols and patient-specific considerations to optimize outcomes for individuals suffering from spinal cord injuries. Further studies are warranted to expand on these findings and to refine treatment guidelines to better serve this patient population in similar healthcare settings.

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